

Moderating Effect of Board Gender Diversity on Operational and Liquidity Risks Information Disclosure and Market Value of Listed Companies in Financial Sector of Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the moderating effect of board gender diversity on the relationship between operational and liquidity risk information disclosure and market value of listed companies in Nigeria's financial sector. Using a Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) approach, data was collected from 432 company-year observations, covering operational risk disclosure, liquidity risk disclosure, and board gender diversity attributes. The findings indicate that board gender diversity significantly moderates the relationship between operational risk information disclosure and market value, enhancing firm performance. However, board gender diversity negatively moderates the relationship between liquidity risk disclosure and market value, suggesting complexities in how diverse boards manage liquidity risk communications. The study concludes that board gender diversity plays a significant role in influencing how risk disclosures affect market value. Specifically, while board gender diversity positively moderates the relationship between operational risk disclosure and market value, it has a negative moderating effect on the relationship between liquidity risk disclosure and market value. Therefore, the study recommends that listed companies in the financial sector should develop and adopt robust risk disclosure frameworks that guide the presentation of operational and liquidity risks. Such frameworks should consider the diversity of the board and how it may influence stakeholder perceptions, ensuring that information is communicated transparently and effectively.

Keywords: Board Gender Diversity, Operational Risk Information Disclosure, Liquidity Risk Information Disclosure, Market Value.

Wordcount: 207

Introduction

In recent years, corporate governance and risk management have garnered significant attention, especially in the financial sector, where proper risk management and transparent disclosure are critical for maintaining market confidence and corporate stability. The importance of operational and liquidity risk information disclosure cannot be overstated, as

it plays a vital role in informing stakeholders about the potential risks a firm faces and its ability to manage them. Operational risk encompasses failures in internal processes, systems, or external events, while liquidity risk involves a firm's ability to meet its short-term obligations. When properly disclosed, these risks provide investors and stakeholders with valuable insights into a firm's health and resilience (Chen et al., 2021).

However, the effectiveness of these disclosures largely depends on the governance structures in place, particularly the composition of the board of directors. Board diversity, which includes aspects such as gender, ethnicity, experience, and educational background, has been identified as a key factor influencing decision-making and overall governance quality. A diverse board is believed to bring a broader range of perspectives and expertise, which may lead to more balanced and comprehensive risk management strategies. This, in turn, could improve how risk information is disclosed to the market, influencing how investors perceive the firm's future performance (Adelegan, 2022; Oyedokun, & Amafa, 2022).

In the context of Nigeria, where the financial sector is a major driver of economic development, the corporate governance structure has been under scrutiny, particularly about how it addresses operational and liquidity risks. The Nigerian financial sector has experienced significant challenges in recent years, including the 2008 global financial crisis and the subsequent regulatory reforms. These events highlighted the need for improved risk disclosure and transparency, as well as better governance practices (Otusanya, 2022). Despite these regulatory efforts, gaps remain in how firms disclose operational and liquidity risks, and how these disclosures are perceived by the market.

The moderating role of board gender diversity is critical in this setting. Research suggests that diverse boards are more likely to advocate for transparent and robust risk disclosures, which can positively affect firm market value. Diverse boards are less likely to suffer from groupthink, and they are more likely to encourage a culture of transparency and accountability. For example, Ishak et al. (2020) found that firms with higher levels of board gender diversity disclosed more comprehensive risk information, which, in turn, had a positive impact on their market value. Similarly, Elamer et al. (2020) noted that diverse boards are better at mitigating the negative effects of risk on firm performance by implementing more effective risk management strategies.

The financial sector in Nigeria plays an important role in the country's economic development, yet it remains vulnerable to various forms of risk, particularly operational and liquidity risks. Operational risk, which arises from internal process failures, and liquidity risk, which concerns a firm's ability to meet short-term obligations, are critical to the stability and performance of financial institutions. Inadequate disclosure of these risks can lead to misinformed decision-making by investors and stakeholders, potentially undermining market confidence and adversely affecting market value (Adelegan, 2022). Despite regulatory requirements for firms to disclose risk information, the quality and comprehensiveness of these disclosures vary significantly across listed companies in Nigeria, raising concerns about the transparency and effectiveness of risk management practices (Ajibade, Oyedokun, & Onibiyo, 2018; Otusanya, 2022).

In addition to this, corporate governance practices, particularly board gender diversity, have been identified as potential drivers of improved risk disclosure. Diverse boards, composed of individuals with different gender, ethnicity, professional backgrounds, and experience, are believed to enhance decision-making and reduce information asymmetry. However, the extent to which board gender diversity influences the relationship between risk disclosure and firm market value remains underexplored in Nigeria's financial sector (Wang et al., 2022). While previous studies have highlighted the positive impact of board gender diversity on general governance practices, there is limited empirical evidence on how it moderates the relationship between specific risk disclosures such as operational and liquidity risks and market performance (Elamer et al., 2020).

Given the regulatory reforms and the economic volatility faced by Nigeria's financial institutions, there is an urgent need to understand how firms can enhance their risk disclosure practices, particularly in the areas of operational and liquidity risks. Furthermore, it is crucial to investigate whether board gender diversity can play a moderating role in this relationship, potentially improving firm performance by fostering more transparent and effective governance. Failure to address these issues may result in poor risk management, reduced market confidence, and weakened financial stability, all of which can have far-reaching consequences for Nigeria's financial system and the broader economy.

Thus, this study seeks to address the following research gap: to what extent does board gender diversity moderate the relationship between operational and liquidity risk information disclosure and market value in Nigeria's financial sector?

Research Objectives

- i. Evaluate the effect of operational risk information disclosure on market value of listed companies in financial sector of Nigeria.
- ii. Determine the effect of liquidity risk information disclosure on market value of listed companies in financial sector of Nigeria.
- iii. Assess the extent to which board gender diversity moderates the relationship between operational risk information disclosure and market value of listed companies in financial sector of Nigeria.
- iv. Determine the extent to which board gender diversity moderates the relationship between liquidity risk information and market value of listed companies in financial sector of Nigeria.

The formulated null hypotheses for the study:

H₀₁: Operational risk information disclosure has no significant effect on market value of listed companies in financial sector of Nigeria.

H₀₂: Liquidity risk information disclosure has no significant effect on market value of listed companies in financial sector of Nigeria

H₀₃: Board gender diversity has no significant moderating effect on the relationship between operational risk information disclosure and market value of listed companies in financial sector of Nigeria.

H₀₄: Board gender diversity has no significant moderating effect on the relationship between Liquidity risk information disclosure and market value of listed companies in financial sector of Nigeria.

Literature Review

Concept of Financial Risk Information Disclosure

Financial risk information disclosure refers to the process by which companies communicate the potential risks that may affect their financial performance, operational stability, or overall market value. Financial risk information disclosure plays a crucial role in enhancing transparency and reducing information asymmetry between firms and their stakeholders. Through risk disclosures, companies provide stakeholders with detailed insights into the various risks they face, including market, credit, liquidity, and operational risks (Mishra, 2020; Hassan & Ibrahim, 2020). These disclosures are essential for fostering investor confidence and helping stakeholders make informed decisions, particularly in sectors like finance where risk exposure can significantly impact performance (Chen et al., 2021; Adelegan, 2022).

Operational Risk Information Disclosure

Operational risk refers to the potential losses resulting from inadequate or failed internal processes, people, systems, or external events. In financial institutions, operational risks can stem from a variety of sources, such as fraud, legal risks, system failures, and external disruptions (Naburgi, Ojo, & Oyedokun, 2024; Ishak et al., 2020; Owolabi, 2023). The disclosure of operational risk information is critical for stakeholders, as it provides them with insights into how effectively a firm identifies, manages, and mitigates such risks. It enhances transparency, enabling investors, regulators, and other stakeholders to assess the firm's risk profile and governance structures (Chung, Lee, & Park, 2022; Ahmad et al., 2022).

According to the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, operational risk disclosure is essential for improving risk management practices and for allowing market participants to better understand a company's exposure to potential disruptions (Gyapong, Monem, & Hu, 2021). As operational risks can be highly unpredictable, consistent and detailed reporting is necessary to build stakeholder confidence, especially in financial institutions that are vulnerable to operational disruptions (Elamer et al., 2020).

Liquidity Risk Information Disclosure

Liquidity risk refers to the risk that a company will not be able to meet its short-term financial obligations due to an inability to convert assets into cash without incurring significant losses (Hassan & Ibrahim, 2020). In the financial sector, liquidity risk is particularly critical as banks and other financial institutions rely heavily on short-term liabilities to fund long-term assets. Therefore, effective management and disclosure of liquidity risks are vital to ensure the stability of these institutions and maintain investor confidence (Chung, Lee, & Park, 2022). Liquidity risk information disclosure involves reporting on a company's exposure to liquidity risks, its policies for managing those risks, and its ability to access liquid assets during periods of financial stress (Elamer et al., 2020; Oyedokun, & Campbell, 2023). The disclosure of such information provides stakeholders with essential insights into how well a firm is positioned to handle liquidity crises. It also reflects the company's transparency and its adherence to regulatory standards, such as the Basel III liquidity coverage ratio (LCR) and net stable funding ratio (NSFR) requirements (Ahmad et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2022).

The importance of liquidity risk disclosure has grown significantly in the aftermath of the 2008 global financial crisis. During the crisis, many financial institutions faced liquidity shortages, which contributed to systemic failures and economic downturns. As a result, regulators and investors have since demanded greater transparency around liquidity management practices (Mishra, 2020). In response, financial institutions worldwide, including those in Nigeria, have been required to enhance their liquidity risk disclosures (Otusanya, 2022; Owolabi, 2023).

Concept of Market Value

Market value serves as a significant measure of a firm's financial health and performance, reflecting investor sentiment and the company's perceived growth potential. It is important to note that market value can fluctuate based on various factors, including market trends, investor behavior, and broader economic conditions (Mishra, 2020). As such, it is not always a direct reflection of the intrinsic value of a firm, which is determined by its fundamentals, such as revenue, earnings, and asset values. According to Borad (2022), a firm's market value is an economic concept that reflects the worth of company in market. The investor's assessment of a company's success is reflected in its market value. Firm market value can increase or decrease because of investors' perception of the vulnerability of the company to

risks and potential threats. In general, every investor uses available information to make investment decisions. When convinced to invest in the stock of such companies, investors respond favourably to accessible information. Investors, on the other hand, respond negatively when public information allows them to avoid investing in such enterprises. Furthermore, investors are usually cautious to avoid investing in stocks that would result in losses (Okpo & Aruwa, 2021).

Concept of Board Gender Diversity

Board gender diversity refers to the inclusion of individuals from various backgrounds, experiences, and perspectives within a company's board of directors. This diversity can manifest in several forms, including gender, ethnicity, age, education, professional experience, and functional expertise. The concept of board gender diversity has gained significant attention in corporate governance literature and practice, as it is believed to enhance decision-making processes, improve corporate performance, and foster innovation (Hassan & Ibrahim, 2020; Chen et al., 2021). Board gender diversity is considered crucial for improving corporate governance by fostering a broader range of viewpoints, reducing groupthink, and increasing the ability to address complex business challenges. It has been linked to better risk management, improved financial performance, and stronger corporate social responsibility (Mishra, 2020).

The modality of managing corporate entities in Nigeria can be said to be rooted in her legal system as the company law in the country recognises the two main organs of business organisation (the board of directors and general meetings) before the emergence of the first code of corporate governance (CG) in the country. The concept of CG simply pays more attention on how a company should be manned by those charged with governance. In other words, the first code issued in 2003 was expected to be used in conjunction to relevant sections of the legislation known as the Companies and Allied Matter Act of 1990, hereafter CAMA by the Nigerian companies, most especially the quoted ones.

Empirical Review

Hassan & Ibrahim (2020) examine the impact of risk information disclosure on firm market value, focusing on the moderating role of board gender diversity. Period from 2010–2018. The study employed panel data regression analysis, using data from 50 listed firms in

Nigeria's financial sector. Board gender diversity was measured using gender and professional background diversity, while risk disclosure was proxied by operational and liquidity risk metrics. The study found that firms with diverse boards disclosed more comprehensive risk information. It further revealed that board gender diversity had a positive and significant moderating effect on the relationship between liquidity risk disclosure and market value but not on operational risk disclosure. While the study provided useful insights into board gender diversity's impact on liquidity risk disclosure, it lacked a robust assessment of other forms of diversity such as age or ethnicity. Additionally, the study's focus on Nigerian firms limits the generalizability of the findings to other regions.

Elamer et al. (2020) investigate the influence of corporate governance, particularly board gender diversity, on the quality of risk information disclosure and its subsequent effect on firm performance 2008–2017. Using a mixed-method approach, the study combined quantitative panel data analysis and qualitative case studies from listed UK financial firms. A fixed-effects regression model was used to determine the relationship between risk disclosure, board gender diversity, and firm performance. The findings showed that board gender diversity, particularly gender diversity, positively moderated the relationship between both operational and liquidity risk disclosures and firm market value. The study indicated that firms with greater diversity in their boardrooms were better equipped to communicate risks to shareholders. This study offered a comprehensive examination of board gender diversity across multiple dimensions. However, its limitation was the sole focus on financial firms in the UK, leaving a gap in its applicability to develop economies like Nigeria, where the corporate governance environment is distinct.

Otusanya (2022) assess the effectiveness of corporate governance mechanisms, especially board gender diversity, in moderating the effects of risk disclosure on corporate performance in the Nigerian financial sector from 2012–2020. This study applied structural equation modeling (SEM) to analyze data from 60 listed financial institutions. It focused on board gender diversity's moderating role on the relationship between risk disclosure (operational and liquidity) and market value. The analysis revealed that operational risk disclosure had a significant negative impact on firm value, but this relationship was weakened in companies with higher board gender diversity. For liquidity risk disclosure, board gender diversity strengthened the positive relationship with firm market value. The study contributed significantly to the discourse on risk disclosure in Nigeria's financial sector. However, it did

not explore other potential moderating factors, such as ownership structure, that could further explain variations in firm value.

Wang et al. (2022) examine how risk management disclosures influence firm value, considering the moderating effect of board gender diversity. Period of Study: 2015–2020. Methodology: This study employed a Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) estimation technique to account for endogeneity in panel data from Chinese financial institutions. Board gender diversity was measured across multiple dimensions, including gender, nationality, and professional expertise. Results: Board gender diversity was found to significantly moderate the relationship between operational and liquidity risk disclosures and market value. Specifically, firms with more diverse boards experienced better market performance when disclosing both types of risks. Although this study presented strong empirical evidence for the moderating effect of board gender diversity, its reliance on financial firms from a single country raises concerns about the applicability of the findings to different corporate governance settings, such as those in emerging markets like Nigeria.

Adelegan (2022) explore the relationship between risk disclosure practices and corporate performance, with board gender diversity acting as a moderating variable. Period of Study: 2010–2019. Methodology: A dynamic panel data model was used, focusing on 40 listed firms in Nigeria. The study utilized GMM to assess the moderating role of board gender diversity in the relationship between operational and liquidity risk disclosure and firm value. Results: The results indicated that board gender diversity, particularly in terms of gender and professional expertise, positively moderated the relationship between liquidity risk disclosure and firm market value. However, operational risk disclosure was found to negatively impact firm value, even with diverse boards. The study offered valuable insights into the Nigerian context. However, it fell short in addressing why operational risk disclosure remained negatively associated with firm performance, even when board gender diversity was high. This points to the need for further investigation into how firms manage operational risks internally.

Theoretical Framework

Signaling Theory

Signaling theory, first introduced by Michael Spence in 1973, explains how one party (the sender) credibly conveys information to another party (the receiver) when there is an asymmetry of information (Michael, 1973). The theory initially arose from Spence's work on job market signaling, where job applicants signal their qualifications to potential employers through education or credentials. The theory has since been adapted to various fields, including corporate finance and governance, where firms signal their quality to investors through disclosures, such as financial statements, risk disclosures, and corporate governance practices. In the context of corporate governance, signaling theory suggests that companies can use disclosures to signal their risk management practices and the quality of their board to external stakeholders. Investors, analysts, and other market participants view the disclosure of critical information, such as credit risk and liquidity risk, as signals of the firm's commitment to transparency and sound governance. These signals reduce information asymmetry and increase confidence in the firm's management, which can enhance the company's market value (Connelly et al., 2011).

Top Echelons Theory

At the top of a firm's performance is the Upper Echelons theory which is based on the premise that organization's performance is substantially influenced by the knowledge, experiences, and competencies of individuals occupying senior managerial positions within the organization (Hambrick & Mason, 1984). Thus, Upper Echelon theory posits that, attributes such as experiences, values, and personalities of members of senior management substantially influence their perceptions of the circumstances they encounter, which ultimately determine their decision-making processes (Hambrick, 2007). The theory suggests that a diverse board comprising individuals of different genders, educational backgrounds, and professional experiences enhances the credibility of the firm's risk disclosures. When a firm with a diverse board discloses operational or liquidity risk information, the market is likely to perceive these disclosures as more reliable and reflective of well-considered governance practices. This perception, in turn, should positively influence the firm's market value. The presence of diverse boards can strengthen the credibility of the signal, as board gender diversity is often associated with better decision-

making, improved risk management, and broader perspectives (Ahmad et al., 2022). Gender, educational, and professional diversity are signals that a firm is committed to progressive and inclusive governance practices, which are viewed favorably by the market. In this way, firms with diverse boards that disclose comprehensive risk information are likely to be seen as lower-risk and better managed, thus enhancing their market value (Elamer et al., 2020).

This study examines the moderating role of board gender diversity on the relationship between operational and liquidity risk information disclosures and market value in Nigeria's financial sector. According to signaling theory, the firm's risk disclosures serve as a signal of its risk management practices to investors. However, these signals may be stronger or more credible when the firm's board is diverse. Several studies (e.g., Wang et al., 2022; Gyapong, Monem, & Hu, 2021) have supported the role of signaling theory in explaining the relationship between corporate disclosures and market value, particularly in the context of board gender diversity. Therefore, signaling theory provides a framework to understand how board gender diversity moderates the impact of risk information disclosure on market value, making it a suitable underpinning for this study. By applying this theory, the study posits that firms with diverse boards are better able to signal the quality of their risk management through operational and liquidity risk disclosures, which in turn enhances their market value.

Methodology

The study adopted an ex-post facto research design as the study relied on the existing data to evaluate relationship existing between an independent variable (financial risk disclosures) and a dependent or outcome variable (market value). The population of the study is all the listed firms in the financial sector of Nigeria. Given the nature of the present study, secondary sources were utilized for data collection. The data for the variables was gathered from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled companies. Additionally, companies' annual reports, accounts of the sampled firms, and relevant publications from the Nigeria Exchange Group (NXG). All market-related data was extracted from the archives and other relevant publications of the NXG/SEC of Nigeria covering the period from 2016 to 2023.

Stochastically, the models are written as follows:

$$CoVal_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CoVal_{it-1} + \beta_2 OPRISK_{it} + \beta_3 LQRISK_{it} + \beta_3 BD_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad \dots\dots\dots$$

Model 1

$$CoVal_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CoVal_{it-1} + \beta_2 BD_{it} + \beta_3 OPRISK_{it} * BD_{it} + \beta_4 LQRISK_{it} * BD_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots \dots \text{Model 2}$$

Table 1 Definition of variables

Symbol	Definition	Measurement	Sources
CoVal	Market Value Or Company Market Value	Tobin's Q is calculated by the ratio of the market value of the firm plus debt divided by the book value of its assets	Endri 2019
OPRISK	Operational Risk	Operational Risk information Disclosure index	Based on Linsley and Shrives (2006)
LQRISK	Liquidity Risk Information	Liquidity risk information disclosure index	Musneh, et al. (2021)
BD	Board Gender Diversity	measured as the percentage of women in the board room)	Hoa and Robert (2007); Peter and Hannu (2017) Qi and Tian, (2012),

Source: Authors, 2024

Results and Discussion of Findings

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Max	Mini	Std. Dev.	Skew	Kurt	Obs
COVAL	0.45863	42.0153	0.00012	1.83800	21.4958	485.801	432
	1	2	2	3	2	8	
OPRISK	4.46481	6.00000	3.00000	0.63059	0.57688	2.85787	432
D	5	0	0	2	7	6	
LQRISK	6.06666	8.00000	5.00000	0.51255	2.58612	12.1249	432
D	7	0	0	1	5	6	
BD	4.37592	6.00000	3.00000	0.63696	0.73064	3.31839	432
	6	0	0	7	2	4	

Source: Result Output, 2024

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics for the key variables examined in this study: Firm Market Value (CoVal), Operational Risk Information Disclosure (OPRISKD), Liquidity

Risk Information Disclosure (LQRISKD), and Board Gender Diversity (BD). Understanding these statistics is critical as they provide insights into the distribution and variability of the data, laying a foundational context for further statistical analyses.

Starting with Firm Market Value (CoVal), the average market value recorded is approximately 0.459. This value suggests that, on average, the firms in the sample exhibit a moderate level of market valuation. The maximum market value observed is 42.015, indicating the presence of some high-performing companies within the dataset that could skew the average upward. Conversely, the minimum market value recorded is 0.000122, which points to certain firms experiencing significantly low market valuations. This disparity in values raises questions about the operational effectiveness or market positioning of these underperforming companies. The standard deviation of 1.838 reveals a high level of variability in market values among the firms, suggesting a heterogeneous landscape where firms differ significantly in terms of their market performance.

The skewness of 21.496 indicates a substantial rightward skew in the distribution of market values. This skewness suggests that a small number of firms with exceptionally high market values are disproportionately influencing the average, potentially masking the performance of a larger cohort of firms that may have lower valuations. Such a high skew could imply that while the market value of a few firms is quite strong, the majority may not reflect similar health. Moreover, the kurtosis of 485.802 points to a highly peaked distribution with heavy tails, indicating the presence of extreme values. The implications of these statistics suggest that the market valuation of firms within the financial sector is not only varied but also influenced by outliers, which necessitates a cautious interpretation of average metrics.

For Operational Risk Information Disclosure (OPRISKD), the mean score is 4.465, reflecting a relatively high level of operational risk disclosure among the firms studied. This level of disclosure could indicate a growing awareness of the importance of operational risk management and transparency in the financial sector. The maximum score of 6.000 shows that certain firms are fully compliant with disclosure expectations, presenting a proactive approach to operational risk management. In contrast, a minimum score of 3.000 suggests that while firms are generally adhering to some level of disclosure, there is still room for improvement. The standard deviation of 0.631 indicates moderate variability in how firms disclose operational risks, revealing that practices are not uniform across the board.

The skewness for operational risk disclosure is 0.577, which indicates a slight rightward skew. This suggests that while most firms are adequately disclosing their operational risks, a few firms are performing exceptionally well in this regard. The kurtosis of 2.858 is close to that of a normal distribution, suggesting that the data are relatively normally distributed with fewer extreme values compared to the market value metrics. This indicates a more stable environment regarding operational risk disclosures among firms in the sample.

Regarding Liquidity Risk Information Disclosure (LQRISKD), the mean score is 6.067, indicating a strong emphasis on liquidity risk information disclosure. This score suggests that firms are prioritizing transparency regarding their liquidity positions, which is crucial for investors and stakeholders. The maximum score of 8.000 signifies that some firms are exceptionally proactive, going beyond the minimum disclosure requirements. The minimum score of 5.000 indicates that all firms in the sample maintain a baseline level of liquidity risk disclosure, which could be a regulatory requirement. The standard deviation of 0.513 suggests low variability in liquidity risk disclosures, implying that most firms adhere closely to similar disclosure practices.

The skewness of 2.586 for liquidity risk suggests a positive skew, indicating that while most firms have high scores in their liquidity risk disclosures, a few may lag behind. Furthermore, the kurtosis of 12.125 indicates a peaked distribution, suggesting the presence of outliers that exhibit significant deviations from the mean. These statistics suggest that while the majority of firms are compliant with liquidity disclosures, there exists a minority that may not meet these standards.

Lastly, examining Board Gender Diversity (BD), the average score is 4.376, suggesting a moderate level of board gender diversity among the firms analyzed. The maximum score of 6.000 reflects that some firms are leading in terms of board gender diversity, which is increasingly recognized as a crucial factor in corporate governance and performance. The minimum score of 3.000 indicates that no firm has a negligible level of diversity, ensuring that all boards exhibit some degree of varied representation. The standard deviation of 0.637 highlights significant variability in board gender diversity across the firms, pointing to differences in how firms approach board composition.

The skewness of 0.731 suggests a mild rightward skew, meaning that most firms possess a satisfactory level of board gender diversity, with a few firms exceeding this standard. The

kurtosis of 3.318 is indicative of a distribution that is slightly peaked, suggesting that while most firms cluster around the mean, there are notable outliers with either very high or low diversity scores.

Table 3: Covariance Analysis

Correlation Probability	COVAL	OPRISKD	LQRISKD	BD
COVAL	1.000000			
OPRISKD	0.023716	1.000000		
LQRISKD	-0.003821	-0.119013	1.000000	
BD	0.033491	0.769718	-0.099637	1.000000
	0.4374	0.0000	0.0206	

Source: Result Output, 2024

Table 3 presents the covariance analysis for the key variables examined in this study: Firm Market Value (COVAL), Operational Risk Information Disclosure (OPRISKD), Liquidity Risk Information Disclosure (LQRISKD), and Board Gender Diversity (BD). This analysis is pivotal as it elucidates the relationships among these variables, providing insights into how they may influence one another and the broader financial performance of listed companies in Nigeria’s financial sector.

The correlation coefficient between COVAL and OPRISKD is 0.023716, which indicates a very weak positive relationship. The associated p-value of 0.5824 suggests that this correlation is not statistically significant at conventional levels (typically $p < 0.05$). This lack of significance implies that changes in operational risk information disclosure do not have a meaningful impact on the market value of firms. It indicates that investors might not be fully considering operational risk disclosures when evaluating market value, potentially pointing to a gap in the communication of operational risks.

The correlation between COVAL and LQRISKD is -0.003821, also demonstrating an extremely weak negative relationship, with a p-value of 0.9294, further confirming a lack of significant correlation. This result indicates that liquidity risk information disclosure does not significantly affect the market value of firms in the financial sector. The absence of a notable relationship may suggest that liquidity risk information is not prioritized by investors when assessing corporate performance.

The correlation between OPRISKD and LQRISKD is -0.119013, revealing a weak negative relationship that is statistically significant with a p-value of 0.0056. This finding suggests that as operational risk information disclosure increases, liquidity risk disclosure tends to decrease, albeit slightly. This could indicate that firms may prioritize one type of risk information over another in their disclosures. A more in-depth investigation would be warranted to understand the potential reasons behind this inverse relationship.

The correlation coefficient between BD and OPRISKD is 0.769718, suggesting a strong positive relationship that is statistically significant ($p < 0.0000$). This implies that firms with greater board gender diversity are more likely to exhibit higher levels of operational risk information disclosure. This finding aligns with existing literature, which suggests that diverse boards may enhance the quality of decision-making and oversight, leading to more comprehensive risk disclosures (Hassan & Ibrahim, 2020; Elamer et al., 2020). Conversely, the correlation between BD and LQRISKD is -0.099637, which suggests a weak negative relationship that is statistically significant ($p = 0.0206$). This may indicate that increased board gender diversity could lead to a reduction in liquidity risk disclosure, although the relationship is not particularly strong. This divergence in correlations hints at the complexity of how board gender diversity influences various aspects of risk information disclosure.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 4: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Variable	Coefficient Variance	Centered VIF
OPRISKD	0.039022	2.464720
LQRISKD	0.024312	1.014530
BD	0.038081	2.454174
C	1.384322	NA

Source: Result Output, 2024

Table 4 presents the results of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) analysis for the key variables examined in this study: Operational Risk Information Disclosure (OPRISKD), Liquidity Risk Information Disclosure (LQRISKD), and Board Gender Diversity (BD). The VIF is an essential metric used in regression analysis to detect multicollinearity, which

occurs when two or more independent variables in a regression model are highly correlated. High multicollinearity can lead to unreliable and unstable estimates of the coefficients.

The VIF value for OPRISKD is 2.464720. A VIF value exceeding 2 is often considered indicative of potential multicollinearity issues, with values above 5 or 10 being more concerning. The value for OPRISKD suggests that while there may be some correlation with other variables, it does not reach a level that would severely compromise the regression analysis. This indicates that operational risk information disclosure can be reasonably included in the model without significant concerns about inflated variance due to multicollinearity.

The VIF value for LQRISKD is 1.014530, which is well below the threshold indicating multicollinearity issues. This low value suggests that liquidity risk disclosure does not have a strong correlation with the other independent variables in the model, indicating that its inclusion will likely not distort the estimates of the regression coefficients.

The VIF for BD is 2.454174, similar to OPRISKD. This value suggests that there is some degree of correlation with other variables but is still within acceptable limits for inclusion in regression analysis. Therefore, while board gender diversity may interact with other variables, it is unlikely to lead to problematic multicollinearity issues.

The VIF analysis highlights that multicollinearity is not a significant concern in this study's regression models. All variables, particularly LQRISKD, display acceptable VIF values, reinforcing the reliability of the estimated coefficients in the regression models. In research, ensuring that VIF values are within a reasonable range is crucial as it helps to maintain the integrity of the findings and conclusions drawn from the analysis.

Table 5: Model 1 GMM Analysis

Dependent Variable: CoVal				
Method: Panel Generalized Method of Moments				
Transformation: First Differences				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
COVAL(-1)	-6.13E-05	0.000226	-0.271498	0.7871
OPRISKD	-0.042043	0.017240	-2.438731	0.0181
LQRISKD	-0.257118	0.047365	-5.428397	0.0000
BD	0.013391	0.013750	0.973886	0.3345
Sum squared resid	3599.118	J-statistic		37.18671
Instrument rank	39	Prob(J-statistic)		0.368626

Source: Result Output, 2024

Table 5 presents the results from the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) analysis for Model 1, where the dependent variable is Market Value (CoVal). This model employs panel data with a first-difference transformation to estimate the relationships between operational risk information disclosure (OPRISKD), liquidity risk information disclosure (LQRISKD), and board gender diversity (BD). The lagged market value (COVAL(-1)) shows a negative coefficient, suggesting that past values of market value have a slight negative impact on current values. However, the high p-value (0.7871) indicates that this relationship is not statistically significant, suggesting that lagged market value does not provide meaningful predictive power for current market value in this context.

The coefficient for OPRISKD is -0.042043, indicating that increased operational risk information disclosure negatively affects market value. The t-statistic of -2.438731 is significant, and the corresponding p-value (0.0181) is below the conventional threshold of 0.05, suggesting a statistically significant relationship. This finding implies that greater disclosure of operational risks may be viewed negatively by the market, potentially due to concerns over the company's risk exposure or management competence. The coefficient for LQRISKD is -0.257118, indicating a strong negative relationship with market value. The extremely low p-value (0.0000) denotes high statistical significance, suggesting that increased liquidity risk disclosure has a substantial detrimental impact on market value. This result indicates that investors may react unfavorably to high liquidity risk disclosures, potentially due to concerns regarding the company's financial health and ability to meet short-term obligations. The coefficient for BD is 0.013391, indicating a positive but statistically insignificant relationship with market value, as suggested by the p-value of 0.3345. This suggests that board gender diversity does not significantly influence market value in the context of this model. It may imply that while diversity might contribute positively, its effect is not substantial enough to be recognized in this specific dataset.

The J-statistic and its p-value (0.368626) are used to test the validity of the instruments employed in the GMM estimation. A high p-value indicates that the null hypothesis of the model being correctly specified cannot be rejected, which suggests that the model is adequately specified with respect to its instruments. The GMM analysis in Model 1 reveals significant insights into the relationships between risk disclosures and market value in

Nigeria's financial sector. The findings indicate that operational and liquidity risk disclosures are negatively correlated with market value, while board gender diversity appears to have no significant effect. These results underscore the importance of understanding market perceptions regarding risk disclosures and the necessity for financial institutions to balance transparency with the potential impacts on their market valuation.

Table 6: Model 2 GMM Analysis

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
COVAL(-1)	-0.000201	0.000184	-1.091296	0.2801
OPRISKD*BD	0.003625	0.001764	2.055293	0.0448
LQRISKD*BD	-0.014425	0.001918	-7.520837	0.0000
Sum squared resid	3598.698	J-statistic		32.30870
Instrument rank	38	Prob(J-statistic)		0.598706

Source: Result Output, 2024

Table 6 provides the results of the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) analysis for Model 2, where the dependent variable is Market Value (CoVal). This model utilizes panel data with a first-difference transformation and incorporates interaction terms to explore the moderating effects of board gender diversity on the relationships between operational risk information disclosure and liquidity risk information disclosure with market value.

The coefficient for the lagged market value (COVAL(-1)) is -0.000201, indicating a negative relationship with the current market value. However, the t-statistic of -1.091296 and the p-value (0.2801) reveal that this relationship is not statistically significant. This suggests that previous market values do not significantly influence current values in this context, reinforcing the findings from Model 1.

The interaction term OPRISKD*BD shows a positive coefficient of 0.003625, indicating that board gender diversity positively moderates the relationship between operational risk information disclosure and market value. The t-statistic (2.055293) is significant, with a p-value of 0.0448, suggesting that greater board gender diversity mitigates the negative impact of operational risk disclosure on market value. This finding highlights the potential value of diverse boards in improving investor perceptions and enhancing market valuation amidst operational risk disclosures.

The interaction term LQRISKD*BD has a coefficient of -0.014425, indicating a significant negative moderating effect of board gender diversity on the relationship between liquidity risk information disclosure and market value. The extremely low p-value (0.0000) and high t-statistic (-7.520837) signify a strong statistical significance. This result suggests that increased liquidity risk disclosures can lead to a more pronounced negative impact on market value in the presence of a diverse board. Investors may perceive diverse boards as less effective in managing liquidity risks, which could drive down market valuations.

The sum of squared residuals indicates the fit of the model, suggesting that it captures a substantial amount of the variation in market value. The J-statistic and its associated p-value (0.598706) indicate that the model is appropriately specified with respect to its instruments, suggesting robustness in the findings. The GMM analysis in Model 2 reveals critical insights into the moderating role of board gender diversity in the relationship between risk disclosures and market value within Nigeria's financial sector. While operational risk information disclosure may be perceived more favorably with increased board gender diversity, liquidity risk disclosures appear to exert a significantly detrimental effect on market value when moderated by board gender diversity. These findings emphasize the complex dynamics at play in investor perceptions of risk and governance, and the importance of considering board composition when assessing corporate disclosures.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) analysis shed light on the relationships between operational risk information disclosure, liquidity risk information disclosure, board gender diversity, and market value in Nigeria's financial sector. This discussion will focus on the implications of these findings and relate them to existing literature.

Operational Risk Information Disclosure and Market Value

The positive moderation of board gender diversity on the relationship between operational risk information disclosure and market value (Coefficient: 0.003625; p-value: 0.0448) suggests that diverse boards may enhance the interpretation and reception of operational risk disclosures by investors. This aligns with the perspective of Adams and Ferreira (2009), who argue that board gender diversity can lead to more effective decision-making processes and

improve the oversight of management. By incorporating varied perspectives, diverse boards may present risk disclosures in a manner that better addresses stakeholder concerns, thereby potentially increasing market value.

In contrast, prior studies have indicated that inadequate operational risk disclosures can negatively affect market valuation due to perceived information asymmetries (Hassan & Ibrahim, 2020). Therefore, the presence of board gender diversity could serve as a buffer against these negative perceptions, enhancing investor confidence in the firm's risk management capabilities.

Liquidity Risk Information Disclosure and Market Value

The findings reveal a significant negative moderating effect of board gender diversity on the relationship between liquidity risk information disclosure and market value (Coefficient: -0.014425; p-value: 0.0000). This suggests that while transparency in liquidity risk disclosures is crucial, the composition of the board can play a critical role in how these disclosures are perceived by investors. Specifically, it implies that increased board gender diversity may be associated with a heightened concern regarding liquidity risk management.

This finding resonates with the work of Chen et al. (2021), which indicates that boards with diverse membership might struggle with cohesiveness, potentially leading to ineffective communication and decision-making in high-stakes situations such as liquidity management. Consequently, when liquidity risk disclosures are presented by a diverse board, investors may interpret this as a signal of potential mismanagement or inefficiency, leading to a decline in market value.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study investigated the moderating effect of board gender diversity on the relationship between operational and liquidity risk information disclosure and market value within Nigeria's financial sector. The findings revealed that board gender diversity plays a significant role in influencing how risk disclosures affect market value. Specifically, while board gender diversity positively moderates the relationship between operational risk disclosure and market value, it has a negative moderating effect on the relationship between liquidity risk disclosure and market value. These results highlight the complexities inherent

in corporate governance and risk management, indicating that while diverse boards can enhance operational risk communication, they may also complicate liquidity risk messaging.

Recommendations

1. To leverage the benefits of board gender diversity effectively, firms should invest in training programs that equip board members with the necessary skills to communicate risk disclosures clearly. These programs should emphasize effective decision-making processes and the importance of cohesive communication strategies, particularly in relation to liquidity risk management.
2. Companies should develop and adopt robust risk disclosure frameworks that guide the presentation of operational and liquidity risks. Such frameworks should consider the diversity of the board and how it may influence stakeholder perceptions, ensuring that information is communicated transparently and effectively.
3. Regulatory bodies should promote initiatives that encourage diversity within corporate boards. This can include setting guidelines that recommend or require diverse representation on boards, thereby enhancing the decision-making process and improving overall corporate governance.
4. Firms should engage in regular assessments of board effectiveness, particularly in relation to risk disclosure practices. By evaluating how well diverse boards communicate risks, companies can identify areas for improvement and make necessary adjustments to governance structures.

References

- Adams, R. B., & Ferreira, D. (2009). Women in the boardroom and their impact on governance and performance. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 94(2), 291-309.
- Adelegan, O. J. (2022). The impact of corporate governance on financial risk disclosures in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Financial Reporting*, 12(3), 145-160.
- Ahmad, M., Hassan, R., & Ibrahim, M. (2022). Corporate governance and firm performance: A critical review of board diversity in emerging markets. *Journal of Business Research*, 23(4), 115-130.
- Ajibade, A.T., Oyedokun, G.E. & Onibiyo, E. (2018). Unsystematic Risk and Financial Performance of Selected Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Taxation and Economic Development*, 17(2). A publication of Chartered Institute of Taxation of Nigeria

- Borad, P. (2022). Board diversity and its effect on risk management and disclosure. *Journal of Corporate Governance*, 14(2), 213-231.
- Chen, C. J. P., Ding, Y., & Zhang, L. (2021). Corporate governance and financial risk disclosure in Chinese firms: The role of board composition. *Asian Review of Accounting*, 29(2), 256-278.
- Chung, H., Lee, J. E., & Park, Y. (2022). Does gender diversity influence risk disclosure and corporate value? Evidence from Asian firms. *Journal of International Business Research*, 32(3), 129-142.
- Connelly, B. L., Certo, S. T., Ireland, R. D., & Reutzel, C. R. (2011). Signaling theory: A review and assessment. *Journal of Management*, 37(1), 39-67.
- Elamer, A. A., Ntim, C. G., Abdou, H. A., Zalata, A. M., & Elmagrhi, M. H. (2020). Corporate governance and risk disclosure: Evidence from multiple theoretical perspectives. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 29(3), 1376-1396.
- Endri, E. (2019). Effect of board diversity on firm performance: Evidence from Indonesia. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*, 17(3), 411-431.
- Gyapong, E., Monem, R. M., & Hu, F. (2021). Board gender diversity and corporate risk disclosure: Evidence from emerging markets. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 21(1), 87-103.
- Hambrick, D. C. (2007). Upper echelons theory: An update. *Academy of Management Review*, 32(2), 334-343.
- Hambrick, D. C., & Mason, P. A. (1984). Upper echelons: The organization as a reflection of its top managers. *Academy of Management Review*, 9(2), 193-206.
- Hassan, A., & Ibrahim, U. (2020). The relationship between board characteristics and risk disclosures in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Management*, 10(2), 34-55.
- Hoa, H., & Robert, H. (2007). The impact of board diversity on risk management in financial institutions. *Journal of Financial Regulation and Compliance*, 15(4), 123-139.
- Ishak, S., Abdul Rahman, R., & Anwar, M. (2020). Board diversity and risk disclosure: A multi-country analysis. *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, 15(2), 321-339.
- Linsley, P. M., & Shrives, P. J. (2006). Risk reporting: A study of risk disclosures in the annual reports of UK companies. *The British Accounting Review*, 38(4), 387-404.
- Michael S. (1973). Job market signaling. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 87(3), 355-374.
- Mishra, P. (2020). Does board gender diversity influence financial risk disclosure? Evidence from Indian banks. *Journal of Management Research*, 12(2), 98-110.
- Musneh, N., Abdullah, H., & Khalid, Z. (2021). The effect of corporate governance on operational risk disclosures in the Middle East. *Asian Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 9(1), 56-73.
- Naburgi, M.M., Ojo, L.O., & Oyedokun, G.E. (2024). Board Attributes and Risk Disclosure of Quoted Industrial Goods Companies Listed in Nigerian Exchange Group. *Lead City Journal of the Social Sciences (LCJSS)*, 9(1), 40-56, a publication of the Faculty of Social

and Management Sciences, Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria

- Okpo, F., & Aruwa, S. A. (2021). Liquidity risk disclosure and firm market value: Evidence from Nigerian banks. *Nigerian Journal of Business and Finance*, 13(2), 45-63.
- Otusanya, O. (2022). Gender diversity and corporate risk disclosure: A case study of the Nigerian financial sector. *African Journal of Accounting, Auditing, and Finance*, 8(1), 210-234.
- Owolabi, R. (2023). Board diversity and its impact on financial performance and risk disclosure among Nigerian listed companies. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 29(3), 237-252.
- Oyedokun, G.E. & Campbell, O. (2023). Imperatives of Risk Analysis and Asset Management on Cyber Security in a Technology-Driven Economy. In F.F. Adedoyin & B. Christiansen, B. (2023). *Effective Cybersecurity Operations for Enterprise-Wide Systems* (Eds.). IGI Global. United Kingdom, 10.4018/978-1-6684-9018-1.ch007; Chapter 7, 147-168. <https://www.igi-global.com/chapter/imperatives-of-risk-analysis-and-asset-management-on-cyber-security-in-a-technology-driven-economy/324921>
- Oyedokun, G.E., & Amafa, E.O. (2022). Claims Payment, Risk Management and Financial Performance of Selected Insurance Companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Insurance and Financial Management*. 6(3), 81-115. <https://journal-of-insurance-and-financial-management.com/index.php/JIFM/article/view/221>
- Peter, D., & Hannu, L. (2017). Gender diversity and risk management in European banks. *European Journal of Finance*, 23(8), 712-735.
- Qi, Y., & Tian, X. (2012). The role of board diversity in financial risk management in Chinese firms. *Journal of Risk Management*, 10(3), 78-95.
- Wang, Y., Sun, L., & Liu, W. (2022). The impact of corporate governance on liquidity risk disclosure: Evidence from listed firms in China. *China Journal of Accounting Studies*, 15(2), 112-135.